

D4.25 Cogwheel Workshop 8

**WP4 Joint integrative
projects**

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: NVI

GENERAL INFORMATION

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REPORT FROM THE 8TH COGWHEEL WORKSHOP BETWEEN OHEJP AND ELIXIR

1. Introduction

In Work Package 4 (WP4) of the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP), EU initiatives that require strategic interaction with OHEJP are identified in collaboration with WP2 and WP5, to avoid redundancy and to further leverage the alignment at EU level. One of the instruments, so called cogwheel workshops (CWs), are being organised by WP4 to allow key actors and relevant partners within the OHEJP, typically Project leaders or WP leaders within Joint Research Projects (JRP:s) or Joint Integrative Projects (JIP:s), to identify synergies, joint priorities and opportunities for collaboration within the OHEJP or with other EU initiatives. Before contacting the relevant EU initiative/project, it is important to identify and collect (common) JRP and JIP needs and to define if the initiative complies with these needs. Furthermore, it is important to see if the initiative can complement or assist the OHEJP, for instance with database/repositories, protocols, advice, practical collaboration (sequencing, bioinformatics) and so on.

Altogether eight CWs have been organised during the OHEJP. The reports from cogwheel workshops will be part of the input to the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) of WP2, as well as the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of WP7.

The target for the 8th CW was ELIXIR (<https://elixir-europe.org/>). ELIXIR is an intergovernmental organisation that brings together life science resources in Europe. The goal is to coordinate the available resources into a single infrastructure. This will simplify finding and sharing data, exchanging expertise and agreeing on best practices.

2. Practicalities

2.1. Practicalities

- In March 2021, WP2 was contacted to get input on relevant projects for the 8th CW scheduled for the autumn 2021. WP2 suggested nine projects, including a document from the ELIXIR project which they had prepared for the OHEJP.
- In parallel, all Project Leaders (PLs), deputies and the Project Management Team (PMT) were asked for input regarding relevant projects for the 8th CW. Deadline for response was set to the middle of April 2021 and ELIXIR was the only project suggested.
- ELIXIR was contacted early May, and gave a positive response for participation in the 8th CW in the middle of May. In collaboration with WP3 and WP4, the date for the workshop was set to September 29th 2021.
- With assistance from the OHEJP communications team, a save the date email was distributed to all OHEJP PLs, OHEJP PhD supervisors, and members of the Scientific Steering Board (SSB), PMT and Communication Contact Person (CCP) in June.
- Link for registration to the workshop was distributed by the OHEJP communications team on September 1st with the registration deadline set to September 15th. The registration form included a list of sub-topics in the ELIXIR project, allowing the participants to indicate topics of special interest. It was also possible to suggest topics for the discussion session of the CW. Information

regarding sub-topics of high interest for the registered participants (see Section 2.3) and suggested topics for the discussion session was provided to ELIXIR before the workshop.

- The workshop was arranged on the 29th of September from 10-12.30 CET.
- Due to technical issues with the Adobe Connect platform during the 7th CW, it was decided to host the 8th CW using the Zoom platform. The OHEJP communications team assisted in providing a link to the meeting and as technical support during the workshop.
- All attendees were informed that the workshop was recorded.
- In total, 68 participants registered for the workshop and 47 participants (including members of the OHEJP administration and ELIXIR) attended the workshop.
- A feedback form was distributed just before the workshop and the deadline for filling in and returning the feedback forms was set to October 13th. In total, twelve feedback forms were received.
- The presentation from ELIXIR was sent to the participants October 13th.
- The OHEJP communications team provided a recording from the workshop which is available together with this report. The closed OHEJP discussion session is not included in this recording.

2.2. Output

2.2.1. Identification of relevant topics within ELIXIR

All OHEJP projects and institutions interested in participating in the CW had the opportunity to do so. On beforehand, the participants were asked to highlight which topics within ELIXIR that were most relevant for them.

ELIXIR topics for the workshop	Registered participants highlighting this topic (%)
Overview and structure of ELIXIR	57.9
Data management and deposition in public databases	66.7
Making data FAIR (interoperability services)	50.9
Software, tools and workflows	63.2
Compute resources	43.9
Bioinformatics training	56.1
ELIXIR's activities in Infectious diseases	66.7
ELIXIR's activities in Biodiversity	19.3
ELIXIR's activities in Other ELIXIR Communities	17.5
Engaging and collaborating with ELIXIR in future	47.4

2.2.2. Summary and general comments

- On beforehand, datasharing (including “sensitive” data) between institutions within and between countries were suggested as relevant topics to discuss in the general discussion session. The background for this suggestion is the need for systems ensuring safe sharing. The technical solutions are available, but the ones available may not be user friendly. Also legal issues and GDPR were mentioned. Other topics mentioned on beforehand were SARS-CoV-2 NGS data and respiratory viruses NGS data.
- ELIXIR is a consortium of member states, so most national node funders are government R&D focused ministries. It is a ministerial decision to become a member of ELIXIR and the country then creates an ELIXIR node, and that node then brings together research institutes and universities to run the services. The board in ELIXIR, the highest decision making body represents the funders of ELIXIR, but the services themselves are run by the academic community.
- During the presentation, the definition of infrastructure was specified - it is more than just the technical focus on hardware, software, databases, etc. The term infrastructure is very broad and includes lot of different components.
- ELIXIR suggested to look into the VEO project <https://www.veo-europe.eu/> for information on sharing metadata etc within and between different institutions. The VEO project was one of the external projects presented in the 7th CW.
- ELIXIR work closely with Common Workflow Language (CWL). The CWL is an open standard for describing analysis workflows and tools in a way that makes them portable and scalable across a variety of software and hardware environments, from workstations to cluster, cloud, and high performance computing (HPC) environments (Commonwl.org). This is a generic adaptable workflow language that can be adjusted to fit different formats e.g., Galaxy. It also can be adopted by KNIME.
- It was suggested that a “One Health” community could be linked to ELIXIR in the long run, as there already is a OH IRIDA/Galaxy community.
- Some institutions and OHEJP projects clearly stated specific action points to approach ELIXIR and to find out more about the ELIXIR Galaxy community, the respective local ELIXIR nodes and look further into topics about storage and relevant tools.
- For the Simulation Exercise (SimEX), ELIXIR could contribute with resources to identify, trace and predict future outbreaks (novel pathogens or AMR).

- Some OHEJP projects have stored WGS data in purpose-built databases to enable posterior curation and analysis. The description and explanation of the training section on bioinformatics from ELIXIR was very fitting for this objective.
- Other topics identified as highly relevant was:
 - The ability to optimize sharing and harmonizing data between sectors at the country level and across countries were of special relevance.
 - A training platform to aid in learning (surveillance focus) was interesting.
 - Overview of the ELIXIR setup and to learn about opportunities and how to arrange long-term access.
 - Data management solutions, compute infrastructure and deployment of containerized software.
 - Solutions to increase interoperability of data and models, e.g. ontologies and data standards.
 - Presented software, tools and workflows.
- It was suggested that OHEJP WP4 should create the context for involvement in ELIXIR and take the lead in any interaction the OHEJP projects might have with ELIXIR. A possible limitation in this suggestion to be aware of is that the participation in ELIXIR is primarily at country level and not at the single institute level.
- In addition to the high interest of the ELIXIR resources, it was also commented that it is high-level and can be a bit challenging to see how we can get it aligned with specific programs.

2.2.3. Summary table Action points

The proposed action points from each project are listed in the summary table below.

Project/Institution	Action points	Who, when
WORLDCOM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share information on ELIXIR • There is no direct need for WORLDCOM to access ELIXIR facilities, but the planners for an OHEJP successor should be aware of the information. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WORLDCOM partners, those involved in planning successor of OHEJP • Once information has been received
DISCoVeR and CARE/VISAVET-UCM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact ELIXIR training providers for more information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immediately after the workshop • Outcome: The project contacted ELIXIR training providers and a positive response with good tips for training was received back from them
BeONE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal consultation on usage of ELIXIR infrastructure both on institute- and EJP-project level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinator of BeONE and National Study Centre for Sequencing in Risk Assessment at BfR • Beginning today, aimed to conclude within 2021
TOXOSOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will continue to follow ELIXIR activities 	
MATRIX	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check out ELIXIR presentation for links to ELIXIR resources relevant for BfR and MATRIX, if necessary create contact to corresponding ELIXIR team members 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BfR • 2021
FED-AMR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metagenomic and WGS analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FED-AMR team • To be defined
Statens Serum Institut	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gather an overview of the current Danish participation in ELIXIR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SSI MATRIX staff • By Dec 2021

2.3. Concluding remarks

The Zoom platform worked out as expected. In general, the ELIXIR presentations received positive feedback, covering highly relevant topics within their infrastructure. However, there is a complex infrastructure and how to handle data in accordance with the law and principles of FAIR are resource demanding. It was therefore suggested that OHEJP WP4 should create the context for involvement in ELIXIR and in further collaboration initiatives with ELIXIR.

3. Presentations

Slides from the presentations given at the CW are included in the Annex. A recording of the meeting can be found here: <https://bit.ly/3bNoeJg>